

PRACTICAL DEMONSTRATION OF FIBRE EVANESCENT WAVE SPECTROSCOPY FOR CURE MONITORING OF EPOXY RESINS USING NOVEL H-GLASS FIBRES

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ABSTRACT

A range of glasses were produced and the refractive index and fibre drawing properties were characterised. The composition H3 was selected and drawn into fibres. The fibres were then used to monitor the cure of Epikote 828 and triethylenetetramine (TETA) epoxy resin system using fibre evanescent wave spectroscopy.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer matrix composites (PMC) are used within many load bearing applications, however under-cured laminates have poor mechanical properties. Therefore, the certainty of cure is of the utmost importance for their use in structural and safety critical applications. As a result, PMC are subjected to conservative processing, involving longer cure dwells and higher cure temperatures, thus resulting in higher residual stresses and an economic disadvantage. Optical [1] and reinforcing [2] glass fibres have previously been used to measure state of cure via fibre evanescent wave spectroscopy (FEWS) in the near infra-red (NIR). However, reinforcing glasses require specialist low refractive index resin systems for light guiding [2] whilst optical fibres are often expensive and produced to a standard 125 μm diameter producing a fibre diameter mismatch with reinforcing fibres resulting in poor compressive properties and resin rich regions that can act as a stress concentrator [3, 4].

To address these issues, various high dielectric constant glass compositions [5] were investigated for suitable refractive index $n_D > 1.63$ (highest RI for epoxy resins), infra-red transmission window and fibre drawing capability. These have then been tested as sensors for conventional high refractive index epoxy resins.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Glasses were produced in batches, designed to give 300g of glass, using two techniques; melting in a platinum crucible using an electric furnace (Pt); or a mullite crucible in a gas furnace (MG). Samples melted in Pt were processed at 1450°C and allowed to melt for 1 hr, followed by 4 hours of stirring with a platinum paddle. MG samples were pre-heated in an electric furnace at 3°C/min to 1000°C, to prevent thermal shock of the mullite crucible, before transferring to the

gas furnace at 1500°C. Gas furnace samples were stirred using a silica rod at 2 and 4 hours before casting at 5 hours. All samples were annealed at 750°C for 1 hour before cooling at 2°C/min to room temperature. The compositions melted are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Composition of H-glasses in mol%

Composition	H1 Pt	H2 MG	H3 Pt	H3 MG	H4 MG	H5 MG	H6 MG
SiO ₂	50.00	50.794	52.08	52.08	51.560	51.550	51.830
Na ₂ O	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
K ₂ O	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
MgO	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
CaO	7.50	9.524	9.38	9.38	7.730	9.280	7.770
SrO	7.50	6.349	6.25	6.25	7.730	6.190	7.770
BaO	15.00	15.873	15.63	15.63	15.460	15.460	15.540
Al ₂ O ₃	0.00	2.646	1.04	1.04	0.000	0.000	0.000
La ₂ O ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
TiO ₂	11.55	9.630	10.31	10.31	11.910	11.910	11.110
ZrO ₂	2.45	2.011	2.19	2.19	2.520	2.520	2.350
Nb ₂ O ₅	6.00	3.175	3.13	3.13	3.090	3.090	3.630

Refractive index measurements were performed on a Horiba-Yvon UVISEL spectroscopic ellipsometer with a 75W Xe lamp over the range 800-400 nm. 2 mm thick samples were polished on one side with a roughened and matt black painted sample rear surface to remove backside reflections. Data was directly converted using Horiba's DeltaPsi2 software.

Density measurements were performed on a Mettler Toledo density measuring kit employing Archimedes' principal. Three samples from each glass were measured and averaged.

Liquidus was measured using a centre wound liquidus furnace with a 24 hour hold and samples in a mullite boat crucible. Samples were then visually analysed for the crystallisation front. Viscosity measurements were taken using a Brookfield DV-III Ultra Rheometer using an alumina crucible.

H3-glass was selected as the most appropriate composition and fibres were produced using an up-drawing technique. H3 cullet was remelted in a Pt crucible using a tube furnace set to 1200°C. A water cooled copper coil was placed above the melt to facilitate rapid cooling of the fibre, preventing melting or burning of the fibre. The fibres were then hand drawn using a silica rod through the cooling coil and attached to a variable speed drum for continuous production.

FEWS experiments were performed by sectioning H3 fibres into 300mm lengths bundling fibres into groups of 35, washing in acetone and isopropanol and threaded through PTFE tubing.

The PTFE tubing was used to align and protect the fibres when inserted into the launch optics and detector holder. These were inserted into a Bentham M300 fibre spectrometer with a PbS sensor as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Bentham fibre spectrometer set up for FEWS cure monitoring of 828 TETA resin

An initial baseline scan of 1000-2500 nm with 10 nm intervals was taken of the H3-fibres for a baseline subtraction. The exposed section of the fibres were covered in the resin Epikote 828 (Delta Resins) and the hardener triethylenetetramine (TETA) (Sigma Aldrich) blend to a mix ratio of 100:30 by weight to give a room temperature curing resin system. Subsequently resin coated fibres were scanned twice every hour for 12 hours, thereby monitoring the cure.

Each set of data was processed according Figure 2 by normalising to the 1st C-H aromatic overtone at 1670 nm then averaging each data set followed by a Beer-Lambert process (shown below in equation 1) in order to subtract the initial baseline scan to reveal the evanescent wave peaks.

$$A = -10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{I}{I_0} \right) (dB)$$

[1]

where A is the resulting baseline subtracted absorption, I is the normalised and averaged spectrum per interval of time and I₀ is the initial baseline spectrum.

Figure 2 Data processing of raw spectrum from fibre evanescent wave spectroscopy.

For comparison a custom made cuvette was produced using microscope slides. 828 TETA resin was added to cuvette and measured using the same parameters as the FEWS cure monitoring.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3 shows the refractive index (RI) of the upper limit of epoxy resins and the RI of H-glass compositions in the visible spectrum (400 – 800 nm).

Figure 3 Ellipsometry RI values of H-glasses with the epoxy resin upper limit

H1 Pt possesses the highest RI of all the H-glass samples. H1 Pt has a roughly similar composition to H4, H5 and H6 but, lower silica and approximately double the Nb₂O₅ level. This corresponds to a higher level of polarisable atoms and resulting high RI. H3 Pt and H3 MG have similar RI's with a slight reduction when melted in mullite. This can be explained by an expected increase in SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ from mullite, resulting in a percentage decrease in the remaining batch. This reduces the overall levels of highly polarisable elements and consequently gives a lower RI and density, shown in Table 2. However, this trend is within the error of ±0.015 and consequently cannot be confirmed.

H2 MG produced the lowest RI, of 1.66, as expected due to the lowest permittivity of all of the glass compositions given in [5] and also having been melted in mullite, where the SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ additions will have further decreased the expected value. Purely looking at H2 MG with lower silica and higher alkali earth ions compared to H3, H5 and H6 it would be expected that a higher RI would be attained. However, the lower density shown in Table 2 would explain a lower RI, in contrast to the compositional considerations. The value of H6 MG was expected to be in line with H4 and H5, with the larger density being expected to correspond to the higher RI. However, this increase cannot be fully confirmed due to the trend being within the region of error ±0.015.

In summary all of the glasses produced possess a suitable RI for light guiding of epoxy resins and consequently can be used for FEWS cure monitoring of epoxy resins.

Table 2 Density and refractive index measurements

Composition	Density (g/cm ³)	RI (590nm) (±0.015)
H1 Pt	3.779	1.72
H2 MG	3.535	1.66
H3 Pt	3.700	1.68
H4 MG	3.604	1.68
H5 MG	3.576	1.68
H6 MG	3.642	1.69

For stable fibre formation a ΔT separation of 50°C is required [6]. The liquidus temperature, log₁₀(η/Poise)=3 fibre forming temperature and the resulting ΔT separation are shown in Table 3 for H1 Pt and H3 Pt samples.

Table 3 Liquidus and viscosity measurements

	T _L (°C) (±5°C)	T(log ₁₀ (η/Poise)=3) (°C) (±5°C)	ΔT
H1 Pt	1176	1102	-74
H3 Pt	1069	1108	39

Samples H1 Pt ΔT at -74°C demonstrates an inability to form fibres as crystallization will instantly occur. H3 Pt possess a positive ΔT demonstrating a poor fibre formability using mullite crucible. Fibre formability of H3 glass given by Komori *et al* [5] in a Pt crucible is 100°C . Consequently H3 glass cullet was melted in a Pt crucible. H3 fibres were successfully drawn producing an average diameter of $55\ \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6 show the peak intensity decrease with time for the peaks at 1540, 2030, 2210nm respectively. The region around 1540 nm (specifically at 1543 nm, which is within the step size of 10 nm used in scanning the spectrum) is the aliphatic secondary amine overtone stretch and the region around 2030 nm (actually 2025 nm) gives the primary amine combination overtone stretch whilst 2210 nm (actually 2208 nm) is the epoxy CH_2 stretch + epoxy CH_2 deformation [1, 7]. All of these peaks will decrease with time as they are used up within the reaction.

Figure 4 Progression of 828/TETA FEWS (left hand y-axis) and 828/TETA cuvette (right hand y-axis) cure monitoring and baseline scan using the normalised 1540nm peak intensity. With an exponential decay trend line. Error bars show 1 standard deviation.

Figure 5 Progression of 828/TETA FEWS (left hand y-axis) and 828/TETA cuvette (right hand y-axis) scans using the normalised 2030nm peak intensity. With an exponential decay trend line. Error bars show 1 standard deviation.

Figure 6 Progression of 828/TETA FEWS cure monitoring using the normalised 2210nm peak intensity. With an exponential decay trend line. Error bars show 1 standard deviation.

Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6 all demonstrate a drop in peak intensity over the first 6 hours followed by a levelling of the signal. This levelling of the signal demonstrates a maximum level of cure. The FEWS peaks trend lines follow a very similar trend to the cuvette baseline scan for 1540 nm and 2030 nm peaks. The 2210 nm epoxy peak was not detected in cuvette baseline scans, this is most likely due to an absorption in the microscope slide. 828/TETA FEWS scans at 2210 nm produces the largest intensity drop demonstrating it as the most suitable peak for cure monitoring of 828/TETA. The FEWS cure monitoring demonstrate a large quantity of noise and preventing an exact quantitative analysis of cure.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A range of glass compositions were melted and all found to be suitable for FEWS cure monitoring. H3 glass was successfully drawn into fibres. FEWS of 828 TETA resin was demonstrated using H3 glass fibres. Cure monitoring was thus found to be possible for conventional epoxy resin systems using a specially selected high refractive index glass sensor material.

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